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AN EXAMPLE ON THE APPLICATIONS OF "SCENARIOS' APPROACH" TO PROBLEMS AFFECTED BY UNCERTAINTY CONDITIONS

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UN ESEMPIO SULL'APPLICAZIONE DELL' "APPROCCIO A SCENARI" A PROBLEMI AFFETTI DA ALTE CONDIZIONI D'INCERTEZZA

ABSTRACT

Viene di seguito riportata una semplice metodologia suggerita, nell'ambito di un rapporto di consulenza, a pianificatori istituzionali di un paese ad economia in via di transizione, per valutare in che modo la costruzione di un tronco di gasdotto con i relativi parametri economici e finanziari possano influire sull'aumento del prezzo del gas per effetto del ripagamento dell'investimento.

La metodologia suggerita ha consentito di ipotizzare scenari che sono stati utili nella pianificazione di nuovi progetti per la generazione di energia elettrica.

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For any country in the world the importance of the gas supply and price is fundamental not only for its economic implications but also for energy security and diversification plans.

Very often, in transition and developing countries such plans are studied and proposed in very high uncertainty conditions due to the lack of historical data and difficulties usually arising during the collection of the basic elements for the preparation of programming proposals. Under such conditions the scenarios' approach is very often adopted.

1. THE GAS - DUCT CASE

The following approach has been suggested to the institutional planners of a transition country in order to evaluate the effect on gas price due to the construction of a new gas-duct section, from the border up to the central region of such a country, while the price of the gas, the gas demand and the investment parameters for the project were totally unknown or at least only a rough estimation of a wide range of such parameters was possible.

According to the hereinafter suggested technique it is possible to draft preliminary scenarios by calculating the *gas price increase* to payback the investment for the section of the gas-duct under different possible hypotheses of the following elements:

- price at the border varying according to an estimated range defined by general international market conditions and negotiation still in progress;
- amount of the investment required for the gas-duct varying according to an estimated range pointed out by a specific scope study;
- payback period for the investment established by the institutional planners in a defined range best fitting with the country policy;
- range of the interest rate dictated by international and local market conditions;

In any case the entire gas demand was assumed to be conveyed through the new gas-duct section.

Hereinafter the way in which the above said gas price increase may be calculated is proposed.

The annual instalment R_a (constant and postponed) to payback the investment is :

$$R_a = \frac{C r q^N}{q^N - 1} \quad (1)$$

where:

C = investment cost in MUS\$ (Million of US Dollars);

r = interest rate

$q = (1+r)$

N = payback period of the investment cost in years.

Each year, due to the gas demand D (in billion cubic meters, GNm^3), with a gas price p (in US dollars per 1000 cubic meters and for gas delivered at the border), the disbursement in MUS\$ is equal to $(D \cdot p)$. In case the investment for the gas-duct is executed, in order to convey gas from the border to the distribution grid, an increase of the gas price $\square\%$ at the delivery points, solely for investment effect (without considering operation and maintenance costs), may be calculated as follows :

$$\Delta\% = 100 \cdot \frac{\Delta p}{p} = 100 \cdot \frac{R_a}{D \cdot p} = \frac{100}{D \cdot p} \cdot \frac{C r q^N}{q^N - 1} \quad (2)$$

According to this algorithm a *Base Case* has been developed with the following data:

- investment cost : 120 MUS\$ (to be considered the most probable “minimum amount” requested for electricity generation purpose only, without taking into consideration the Country total gas demand which may require a larger investment);
- payback period : 15 years ;
- rate of interest : 12 % ;

- price at the border : variable from 50 US\$/kNm³ up to 85 US\$/kNm³ (step 5);
- gas demand : variable from 2,5 GNm³ up to 5 GNm³ (step 0.5).

For the *Base Case* the result is that the range of gas price increase is within 3% and 14% of the price at the border (as shown in Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Other cases to be considered as *Variations to the Base Case* have been developed according to the following hypotheses (refer to the table and chart attached herewith):

- investment cost : from 80 MUS\$ up to 220 MUS\$ (step 20);
- payback period : from 5 years up to 40 years (step 5);

- rate of interest : from 4% up to 18% (step 4).

The *Variations to the Base Case* clearly show that in the worst case a gas price increase of about 25% may be possible.

2. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF THE INCREASE $\Delta\%$ OF THE GAS PRICE

In order to develop the sensitivity analysis of the increase

$$\Delta\% = \frac{100 C}{D p} \cdot \frac{r q^N}{q^N - 1} \quad (2')$$

of the gas price, we calculate the relative variation of $\Delta\%$ as a function of C% (relative variation in % of the investment Cost), D% (relative variation in % of the gas Demand), p% (relative variation in % of the gas price), $\delta r\%$ (relative variation in % of the interest rate) and N% (relative variation in % of the payback period) utilising the method of the relative differential.

Therefore differentiating Eq.(2') and dividing the result by $\Delta\%$ we obtain the following relation:

$$\frac{d(\Delta\%)}{\Delta\%} = + \frac{dC}{C} - \frac{dD}{D} - \frac{dp}{p} + \left[\frac{q^N - 1 - r N q^{-1}}{q^N - 1} \right] \cdot \frac{dr}{r} - \left[\frac{N \ln q}{q^N - 1} \right] \cdot \frac{dN}{N} \quad (3)$$

which can be rewritten as follows:

$$(\Delta\%)\% = +C\% - D\% - p\% + \left[\frac{q^N - 1 - r N q^{-1}}{q^N - 1} \right] \cdot \delta r\% - \left[\frac{N \ln q}{q^N - 1} \right] \cdot N\% \quad (4)$$

As we can see, Eq.(4) shows the quantitative effects of each variation of the parameters C, D, p, r, and N on $\Delta\%$.

The most probable case is the “Base case” which is characterised by the following values:

$$N=15$$

$$r= 12\%,$$

then, the coefficients of the fourth and fifth addenda at right side of Eq.(4) will have the following values:

$$\left[\frac{q^N - 1 - r N q^{-1}}{q^N - 1} \right] = 0.64$$

$$\left[\frac{N \ln q}{q^N - 1} \right] = 0.38$$

Consequently Eq.(4) becomes as follows:

$$(\Delta\%)\% = +C\% - D\% - p\% + 0.64 \delta r\% - 0.38 N\% \quad (4')$$

Therefore we have the following results:

- 1) An increment in percent of the investment Cost shall be reflected in an identical increment of the gas price increase;
- 2) An increment in percent of the gas Demand shall be reflected in an identical decrement of the gas price increase;
- 3) An increment in percent of the gas price shall be reflected in an identical decrement of the gas price increase;
- 4) An increment in percent of the interest rate shall be reflected in an increment of the gas price increase reduced by a factor 0.64;
- 5) An increment in percent of the payback period shall be reflected in a decrement of the gas price increase reduced by a factor 0.38.

Fig. 2

3. CONCLUSIONS

The adopted methodology and the related outline produced for different scenarios have been useful in the planning of the new energy generation projects, giving the possibility to analyse the

influence of gas price on generation costs under several hypothesis (technical, economic and financial) for the new gas duct section.

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